

Perceptions of Sustainability in the Greek Hospitality Sector:

Exploring Motivations, Values, and Sustainable Strategies

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by

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ABSTRACT

This dissertation investigates perceptions of sustainability within the Greek hospitality sector, with a specific focus on Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs). The central aim is to explore the motivations, values, and strategies behind the adoption of sustainable practices, alongside the barriers SMEs face in this regard. The research provides key insights into how sustainability principles are understood and implemented in tourism, one of Greece's most critical industries.

A quantitative approach was adopted, involving a survey of 72 accommodation providers across Greece. The data collected through structured questionnaires focused on sustainability perceptions, motivations, and practices. The responses were analysed using statistical methods to identify trends and relationships between variables such as business size, geographical location, and sustainability efforts.

The research revealed that the primary motivations for adopting sustainability were cost savings (40%) and improving business reputation (26%), while eco-friendly values and personal fulfilment were significant guiding principles. The most widely implemented strategies included reducing energy consumption (37%) and sourcing local products (28%). However, more advanced initiatives such as waste management and carbon footprint reduction were less prevalent. The study also highlighted significant barriers to sustainability adoption. High costs (50%) and uncertainty regarding return on investment (25%) were the main challenges faced by SMEs. Additionally, a lack of knowledge about sustainability certifications was a critical factor limiting broader certification adoption, with 72% of respondents lacking any certification.

The findings underscore the need for targeted financial incentives, greater awareness, and education programs tailored to SMEs in the hospitality sector. By addressing these barriers, SMEs can more effectively implement sustainability strategies, thereby improving both environmental outcomes and long-term profitability. Furthermore, the study contributes to the broader discourse on sustainable tourism by offering a detailed case study of the Greek context, highlighting the complexities and opportunities inherent in aligning business practices with sustainability goals. To overcome these barriers, the study recommends the introduction of region-specific training programs to raise awareness of the benefits of certification, enhanced government support through subsidies, and the development of regional sustainability networks to facilitate resource sharing and collaboration among SMEs.

While the study offers valuable insights, it is limited by the relatively small sample size and the focus on self-reported data, which may introduce bias. Future research should explore qualitative methods to gain a deeper understanding of the motivations and challenges faced by individual businesses. Furthermore, expanding the scope to include larger enterprises and other sectors within the tourism industry could provide a more comprehensive view of sustainability practices in Greece.

Keywords:

Sustainability, SDG & Greek Hospitality, Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in Hospitality, SDG Motivations, Sustainability Certifications, Sustainability Financial Incentives

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PREFACE

My journey into the world of sustainability began during a summer vacation in a small, picturesque village in Crete - Greece. I was captivated by the natural beauty and the harmonious coexistence of the local community with their environment. The villagers' respect for nature and their sustainable practices in everyday life left a profound impression on me.

Another significant source of inspiration has been my brother Harris, who runs his business in hospitality in Crete. Observing his dedication to implementing sustainable practices in his hotel operations has greatly influenced my understanding and appreciation of sustainability in the hospitality sector. His commitment to creating an eco-friendly environment for his guests, demonstrated the tangible benefits and challenges of integrating sustainability into the industry.

This experience sparked my curiosity about how such principles could be integrated into the larger, more commercial sectors of our society. As I pursued my studies in management, I realized the significant impact that sustainable practices could have on the tourism industry. This realisation led me to explore the motivations, values, and practices behind sustainability in the Greek hospitality sector.

Through this dissertation, I aim to delve deeper into these aspects, hoping to contribute to a more sustainable future for the industry and beyond.

ABBREVIATIONS

CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
GRI	Global Reporting Initiative
INSETE	Institute of the Greek Tourism Confederation
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
OWG	United Nations General Assembly's Open Working Group on Sustainable Development Goals
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
UN	United Nations
UNEP FI	United Nations Environment Programme Finance Initiative
UNGC	United Nations Global Compact
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organization
WBCSD	World Business Council for Sustainable Development
WCED	United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Tourism is a key contributor to the worldwide economy, currently it has a significant impact on both the social and environmental conditions of tourism destinations (UNWTO, 2020). Still, not much research has been conducted on the motives of tourism operators for participating with environmentally friendly practices (Kornilaki et al., 2019).

Since the most serious phase of the COVID-19 appears to have passed, the tourism sector is being urged to rebuild tourism in a more effective, sustainable way by promoting environmentally friendly production and utilization (Ateljevic, 2020).

Although increased focus on the application of sustainable practices by businesses in the last decade, it continues to be an absence of research related to eco-savings and environmental policies. The situation is particularly relevant for hospitality SMEs, which may be attributed to the sector's lack of institutional policies regarding sustainability (Font and Lynes, 2018). As a result, there is plenty of potential to investigate the spectrum of sustainability strategies utilized by hospitality SMEs (Kornilaki, Thomas, and Font, 2019). Accommodation contributes significantly to CO₂ emissions, whereas SMEs make up a significant portion of the tourism sector. Research on the factors that influence sustainable conduct, including principles and motivations, is limited. Consequently, additional research seems appropriate at the confluence of values and reasons to become a tourism accommodation entrepreneur.

Greece has made significant strides in enhancing its sustainability efforts through initiatives like the "Recovery and Resilience Facility," aimed at promoting a sustainable socio-economic model. By 2020, Greece doubled the share of Renewable Energy Sources in energy consumption to 21.7%, indicating the nation's commitment to a sustainable future (Hellenic Government, 2022).

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

This research aims to facilitate the movement towards a more sustainable and fair tourism sector, focusing on SMEs. The primary goal of this thesis was to gain a deeper insight into the factors that drive sustainable behaviour among tourism entrepreneurs and how these factors influence their sustainable strategies.

The primary objectives to be achieved through this research study are:

- 1. To Explore the Motivations and Values for Sustainability Adoption in the Greek Hospitality Sector**
- 2. To Examine the Sustainability Practices Adopted by SMEs in the Greek Hospitality Sector**
- 3. To Identify the Barriers to Sustainability Adoption in Greek Hospitality SMEs**

1.3 Research Questions

The central research question guiding this study is:

- ❖ **How do values, motivations, and implemented sustainability measures influence sustainable practices within entrepreneurs in the Greek hospitality sector?**

Sub-Research Questions: To address the overarching research question effectively, the following sub-questions will be explored:

1. What are the core values underpinning sustainable initiatives in the Greek hospitality context?
2. What are the primary motivations driving stakeholders within the Greek hospitality sector to adopt sustainability measures?
3. What sustainability measures are currently being implemented by players in the Greek hospitality market?
4. What are the challenges and barriers encountered in the implementation of sustainable practices in Greece?
5. What strategies can be recommended to enhance the integration of sustainability principles into the strategic planning and operational frameworks of Greek hospitality businesses?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review draws on extensive research, incorporating a wide range of sources. This review encompasses theoretical frameworks, key concepts, empirical studies, and best practices relevant to sustainable tourism, value and motivations orientations influencing the sustainable behavior.

2.1 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and Their Impact on Hospitality

On September 25, 2015, the UN General Assembly adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which included 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (**Figure 1.**). These goals provide a global framework for addressing sustainability challenges (UN 2015b). While the SDGs aim to balance social, environmental, and economic development, several critics argue that they often emphasize economic growth at the expense of social well-being and environmental protection (Glavič and Lukman, 2007). This criticism is particularly relevant in the context of hospitality, where economic pressures can clash with ecological priorities.

Figure 1.: 17 Sustainable Development Goals

Source: United Nations, <https://www.un.org>

The hospitality sector, dominated by SMEs, struggles to fully integrate SDG principles, especially when sustainability practices increase operational costs (Melissen et al., 2016). While some large-scale hotel chains have adopted SDG-aligned strategies, SMEs are lagging, often due to a lack of institutional policies (Font and Lynes, 2018). This creates a gap in sustainability research, as much of the existing literature focuses on the practices of major hospitality corporations, leaving SME dynamics underexplored (Kornilaki & Font, 2019).

2.2 Challenges of Sustainable Practices in the Hospitality Sector

Despite the growing recognition of sustainability's importance, the hospitality industry, particularly SMEs, remains far from fully sustainable. Accommodation providers contribute significantly to CO₂ emissions and resource depletion (UNWTO, 2020). Research by Kornilaki, Thomas, and Font (2019) highlights that while sustainability initiatives such as eco-certification programs and energy-saving technologies are available, many businesses in the sector, particularly SMEs, fail to adopt them. A primary reason is the perceived imbalance between costs and long-term benefits.

Most studies emphasize the environmental aspects of sustainability, often ignoring the social and cultural dimensions, which are equally critical to the hospitality sector's sustainable development (Gössling et al., 2020). Furthermore, existing research often lacks comprehensive empirical data, especially in assessing the long-term economic benefits of adopting sustainability practices (Jones & Comfort, 2020). The limited focus on methodological rigor in studies on SMEs' sustainability strategies highlights an area that needs further exploration. This research will attempt to address these shortcomings by focusing on smaller accommodations within Greece, an area where sustainability adoption has been under-researched.

The concerns and queries with respect to the future growth of hospitality companies have established a path over the sustainable growth of the tourism industry (Font, Garay and Jones, 2016A) as an answer toward the sector's unfavorable future outlook in order to motivate the business community to environmentally friendly approaches (Chang et al., 2020; Romagosa, 2020). Yet, similar discussions have occurred throughout earlier crises (Sheldon & Dwyer, 2010), raising concerns about the hospitality sector's potential to stay on course for future growth following the COVID-19 pandemic (Jones & Comfort, 2020). Therefore, lessons learned from previous crises might guide upcoming strategic decisions of companies in hospitality.

2.3 Preconditions for ecological behavior

As Font et al., (2016B) emphasize, entrepreneurs with small businesses rarely define their company-wide policies and the adoption of sustainability initiatives is largely informal. The strategies implemented reflect their personal preferences and values. Additionally, people are unable to designate their behavior as sustainable, regardless of whether they offer value to community and the natural environment (Font, Garay, and Jones, 2016A). Findings demonstrate that many tourism accommodation operators weigh the financial advantages and disadvantages of sustainable initiatives (Font, Garay, & Jones, 2016). Based on the entrepreneur's values and motives, they may weigh the advantages for environment and society (Sardianou et al., 2016).

Since there exists a wealth of literature on sustainability initiatives that are adopted by accommodations (Suárez-Cebador et al., 2018), the explanations why entrepreneurs use these strategies to indicate sustainable conduct are not as widely recognized (Garay et al., 2017).

Two significant preconditions for sustainable conduct have been suggested: a) values, according to Steg, (2016) and b) motivation, according to Stern et al., (1999), which can be observed as the reasons to behave ecologically (Gast, et al., 2017) (**Figure 2**).

Figure 2: Preconditions for ecological behavior (Gast, et al., 2017)

Source: Own designing

2.4 Values influencing sustainable behavior

Values play a pivotal role in determining whether businesses adopt sustainable practices. According to Cavagnaro and Curiel (2017), there is a growing consensus that sustainability demands the creation of value on the social, ecological, and economical parameters, as well as at the level of businesses. The accommodation business has just recently become concerned with sustainability, and it has been criticized for focusing solely on the environmental aspect, notably eco-efficiency initiatives (Font and Lynes, 2018). While a few findings suggest that the hospitality industry is beginning to see sustainability in broader perspective research has primarily focused on major hotel companies, leaving tourism SMEs underrepresented (Kornilaki and Font, 2019). It thus becomes necessary to investigate how SME tourism business owners comprehend sustainability, along with whether and what sustainability initiatives they adopt.

As stated by Stern et al. (1995), values determine life objectives, and so influence the motivation as well as behavior essential to achieve those objectives. Ethics affect sustainable behavior, which includes minimizing energy use, while clarifying why certain people will implement environmentally friendly approaches. (Steg, 2016).

According to Hemingway (2005), morals are particularly essential in the decision-making process of business owners since they impact their objectives and vision for their company's success. Lindenberg and Steg (2007) highlighted four significant approaches, (**Figure 3**), that have a demonstrable influence on sustainable behaviors: (a) emotion values, which show "being greater fulfillment now"; (b) self-focused values, which reflect "preserving and improving one's individual wealth"; (c) humanitarian values, which represent "a concern for the wellbeing of other humans"; and (d) eco-friendly values, which express concern for ecosystems and planet protection.

Figure 3: Values influencing sustainable behavior (Lindenberg and Steg, 2007)

Source: Own designing

While much of the literature recognizes the role of values in promoting sustainability, it tends to overemphasize environmental motivations while underplaying other influencing factors like social and economic values. Additionally, most studies do not adequately differentiate between values in large-scale organizations and those in SMEs, which is a critical oversight given that SMEs often operate on different economic and operational principles (Font & Garay, 2016). This research will address these gaps by focusing on how value-driven sustainability differs among SME entrepreneurs in Greece's hospitality sector, where cultural and regional factors may also play a role.

2.4 Motivations' classification for sustainable behavior

Motives and motivations, on the other hand, are often used in research on entrepreneurship, including common-sense theory and the theory of identity. According to the literature review, only a few studies have accurately characterized both of these terms. Mitchell (1982) defined motivation as “psychological mechanisms that induce the excitement, focus and tenacity of voluntary behaviors which are purpose oriented”.

Font et al. (2016B) categorized motivations for sustainability in SMEs into three primary areas: cost reduction and innovation, sociological legitimacy, and lifestyle choices (**Figure 4**). For SMEs in the hospitality sector, financial concerns often dominate decision-making, with entrepreneurs primarily motivated by potential cost savings from sustainability measures such as energy efficiency or waste reduction (Font et al., 2016B). However, sociological legitimacy gaining approval from stakeholders like customers, the local community, and governments also play an important role in shaping sustainable behaviors.

Figure 4: Motivations' classification for sustainable behavior (Font et al., 2016B)

Source: Own designing

There is a growing body of evidence suggesting that cost concerns are a dominant barrier to sustainability adoption among SMEs (Sardianou et al., 2016). However, this perspective often oversimplifies the complexity of SME decision-making processes, which are influenced by a combination of personal values, lifestyle preferences, and market pressures (Gast et al., 2017).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Philosophy and Approach

This research is guided by the principles of positivism, which aligns with the use of objective, empirical data to uncover patterns and relationships between variables. Positivism, as a research philosophy, assumes that reality exists independently of human interpretation and can be measured using structured methods, such as surveys and statistical analysis (Bryman, 2012). In the context of this study, positivism supports the collection of quantitative data to explore the relationship between sustainability values, motivations, and behaviours among hospitality SMEs in Greece. The emphasis on objective measurement and generalisation is key, as the study aims to identify patterns that can be applied to a broader population of accommodation providers (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

The research also follows a deductive reasoning approach, which begins with established theories related to sustainable behaviour and applies them to the specific context of Greek SMEs. Deductive research involves moving from the general to the specific, starting with theoretical propositions and testing them through data collection (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In this case, the study draws on established frameworks, such as Stern et al.'s (1995) theory of value-based environmental behaviour and Font et al.'s (2016) classification of motivations for sustainable behaviour in tourism SMEs, to develop hypotheses regarding the relationship between values, motivations, and sustainability practices.

3.2 Rationale for Quantitative Research Design

The choice to use a quantitative research design stems from the nature of the research questions and the objectives of this study. Quantitative methods were selected because they allow for the systematic measurement and analysis of key variables, such as sustainability motivations, values, and behaviours among accommodation providers. This approach is particularly suited to testing relationships between variables, which is a core aim of this study specifically, to assess how values and motivations influence the adoption of sustainability strategies in the Greek hospitality sector. The structured nature of quantitative methods ensures replicability and facilitates comparative analysis across different types of accommodations (Bryman, 2012).

3.3 Sample Selection Process

Greece has a substantial number of accommodations to cater to its significant tourist influx. According to recent data, there are approximately 10,052 hotel units with around 456,238 rooms, alongside over 305 campgrounds and 2,500 small houses operating throughout the country (INSETE, 2024). This extensive infrastructure suggests that a considerable portion comprises SMEs enterprises, as these are prevalent in the tourism and hospitality sector (Visit Greece, 2024).

This study aimed to survey 100 accommodation providers across Greece, both on the mainland and the islands. The sample was selected using a purposive sampling method. This approach was chosen because it allowed to target a specific group of businesses (SMEs enterprises) that are most relevant to the study's focus on sustainability in the hospitality sector.

The selection process began with identifying accommodation providers that met the following criteria:

- The businesses had to be **SMEs**, which according to European Commission guide (EC, 2020) means employing fewer than 250 employees.
- The accommodations had to be located in **key tourism regions** of Greece, including both popular island destinations and mainland locations, ensuring a representative sample of the national tourism landscape.

These providers were identified through publicly available databases such as **Visit Greece**, **INSETE** and received invitations to participate in the survey. Accommodations were chosen to represent a mix of different types (e.g., hotels, guesthouses, resorts) and sizes (small, medium, and large within the SME category) to capture a diversity of perspectives on sustainability practices.

The regions and accommodation types were selected to ensure a diverse representation of the Greek hospitality landscape, particularly focusing on areas with **significant tourism activity**. Certain regions, such as the islands of **Crete** and **the Ionian Islands**, and mainland locations like **Attica**, were chosen **for their tourism prominence**. This was critical to capturing a balanced view of sustainability practices across both **high-density tourism zones** and smaller, niche markets. **Boutique hotels**, for example, were **prioritised due to their unique positioning** in the hospitality sector, often emphasising sustainability as a competitive advantage.

3.4 Participant Characteristics

The survey achieved a response rate of 72%, with responses from 72 accommodation providers out of 100 of them.

The distribution of the participants by type of accommodation and size is detailed in the Table 3.1, ensuring that a diverse range of perspectives on sustainability was captured. The table provides an overview of the distribution of responses by various demographic and operational factors, such as location (island vs. mainland), size of the accommodation, and type of accommodation (e.g., hotel, guesthouse).

Table 3.1: Participant Characteristics

Characteristic	Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
Location	Island	38	52
	Mainland	34	48
Type of Accommodation	Hotel	13	18
	Boutique Hotel	33	46
	Guesthouse	19	26
	Resort	7	10
Size of Accommodation	<20 rooms	5	7
	Small 20 – 49 rooms	40	56
	Medium 50 - 99 rooms	23	32
	>100 rooms	4	6
Years in Operation	Being established	7	10
	<5 years	15	21

Characteristic	Category	Number of Responses	Percentage (%)
	5-10 years	29	40
	>10 years	21	29

As Table 3.1 reveals, out of the 72 respondents, 52% (38 accommodations) are located on islands, while 48% (34 accommodations) are on the mainland. This distribution indicates a slightly higher participation from island-based accommodations. The majority of respondents are Boutique hotels (46%, or 33 accommodations), with guesthouses making up 26% (19 accommodations). This shows a dominant representation of traditional hotels in the sample. Small accommodations are the most common (56%, or 40 accommodations), followed by medium (32%, or 23 accommodations) and large accommodations (6%, or 49 accommodations). This reflects a significant presence of smaller-sized businesses in the sector. A diverse range of experience levels is represented, with 21% (15 accommodations) having less than 5 years of operation, 40% (29 accommodations) operating for 5-10 years, and 29% (21 accommodations) being in business for more than 10 years. This indicates a balanced mix of newer and more established businesses.

3.5 Survey Instrument

To collect data for this research, an online survey was employed as the primary instrument¹. Online surveys are widely recognized for their efficiency and ability to reach a geographically dispersed sample (Evans & Mathur, 2005), making them ideal for studies like this. The survey was designed with 15 closed-ended questions, allowing respondents to select from pre-defined options, which facilitated the collection of structured, quantitative data.

The online format allowed respondents to complete the survey at their convenience, which can improve response rates, especially in time-sensitive industries like hospitality (Wright, 2005). Furthermore, the use of an online platform ensured anonymity and confidentiality, which are crucial for mitigating response bias and encouraging honest responses (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

The questions were designed based on the literature review and theoretical frameworks provided by Stern et al. (1995), Steg (2016), Hemingway (2005), Lindenberg and Steg (2007), and Font et al. (2016A).

The full questionnaire is available in Appendix 1 for further reference.

3.6 Data Analysis

The collected data were analysed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were digitalised to summarise the characteristics of the respondents and their responses (Fowler, 2014; Pallant, 2020) and provided a summary of the data, including the frequency and percentage of responses for each question. Inferential statistics, such as t-tests and ANOVA, were used to examine differences in sustainability perceptions and practices based on demographic variables (e.g., type of accommodation, size of establishment) (Field, 2017; Cohen, 1988).

¹ <https://s.surveypal.com/hz6n8w4y>

3.7 Limitations of the Study

While this study provides valuable insights into the sustainability practices of SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector, several limitations should be acknowledged.

Sample Size and Representativeness

One limitation of this research is the sample size. Although efforts were made to survey a diverse group of 100 accommodation providers, the final response rate was lower than anticipated, with only 72 completed surveys. This relatively small sample size may limit the generalisability of the findings to the broader population of SMEs in Greece. While this sampling method ensures relevance, it can introduce sampling bias and limit the study's ability to reflect the full diversity of the hospitality sector, particularly larger businesses or accommodations operating in different economic contexts (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019).

Self-Reported Data and Potential Bias

The study relied on self-reported data collected through surveys, which can introduce certain biases. Participants may have provided responses that align with socially desirable behaviors, particularly on topics like sustainability, where respondents may wish to appear more environmentally conscious than they actually are (Podsakoff et al., 2003).

Quantitative Method Limitations

The use of a quantitative approach limits the depth of understanding that could be gained from qualitative methods such as interviews or case studies. While quantitative methods allow for the identification of patterns and relationships between variables, they do not provide in-depth insights into the contextual or subjective experiences of the participants (Bryman, 2012).

Timing of Data Collection

The data for this study was collected following the COVID-19 pandemic, a period of significant disruption for the hospitality industry. The economic and social effects of the pandemic may have influenced how accommodation providers view and implement sustainability practices. As such, the findings may reflect a unique set of circumstances that could change as the industry continues to recover, potentially affecting the long-term applicability of the results.

3.8 Ethical Considerations

To ensure that this study adhered to the highest ethical standards, several measures were implemented throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. Participants were provided with a clear explanation of the research purpose, procedures, and their rights, including the right to withdraw from the study at any point without penalty. The anonymity and confidentiality of all respondents were strictly maintained, with all data being stored securely and used solely for academic purposes. No identifying information was collected, and responses were anonymized to protect participants' privacy (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2019). Finally, to prevent any harm or discomfort, participants were assured that the questions focus on business operations and sustainability practices.

4. FINDINGS / DATA ANALYSIS / EVALUATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the results of the research conducted to explore the sustainability practices, motivations, and challenges faced by SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector. The primary aim of this chapter is to analyse the data gathered through survey from **72 accommodation providers** and to interpret the findings in relation to the research objectives outlined in earlier chapters. First, the demographic profile of respondents is presented, followed by an exploration of how businesses perceive the importance of sustainability. The chapter then delves into the key motivations for adopting sustainable practices and examines the specific sustainability strategies that have been implemented by accommodation providers.

Additionally, this chapter addresses the barriers that hinder further adoption of sustainability measures and evaluates the perceived impact of these practices on profitability. Finally, the chapter concludes by exploring the level of certification among respondents and their future intentions regarding investment in sustainability.

4.2 Data Analysis

4.2.1 Profile of Participants

The survey sought to understand the nature of the accommodations in terms of years in operation, type of accommodation, and size. This information helps frame how established businesses may differ in their approach to sustainability. The participants answered how long has the accommodation/establishment been in tourism operation.

Table 4.1 illustrates that 40% of accommodations have been in operation for **5-10 years**, while 29% have been established for **more than 10 years**. Businesses with more experience may have more resources and established strategies, potentially contributing to a more mature approach to sustainability. However, the 21% of businesses in operation for **less than 5 years** may reflect newer entrants that could be more agile in adopting innovative sustainability measures, though they might face financial constraints.

Table 4.1: Q1. How long has your accommodation/establishment been in tourism operation?

Table 4.1: Q1. How long has your accommodation/establishment been in tourism operation?		
Years in Operation	Percentage	Count
Being established	10%	7
Less than 5 years	21%	15
5-10 years	40%	29
More than 10 years	29%	21
Total	100%	72

This distribution is relevant for understanding how the length of time in operation may influence the adoption of sustainable practices. More experienced businesses might have more established

processes for sustainability, whereas newer businesses may be more adaptive but also face challenges in implementation due to resource constraints.

As shown in **Table 4.2**, **boutique hotels** constitute the majority of the sample (46%), followed by **guesthouses** (26%), **hotels** (18%) and **resorts** (10%). Boutique hotels may prioritize sustainability more due to their niche positioning and unique market offerings, where environmental responsibility can serve as a key differentiator. The focus of boutique hotels on sustainability may also be driven by customer expectations in this segment.

Table 4.2: Q2 What type of accommodation do you own/manage?

Table 4.2: Q2. What type of accommodation do you own/manage?		
Type of Accommodation	Percentage	Count
Hotel	18%	13
Boutique Hotel	46%	33
Guesthouse	26%	19
Resort	10%	7
Other (please specify)	0%	0
Total	100%	72

This variety of accommodation types allows for an understanding of how sustainability efforts may differ across business models. For example, boutique hotels might prioritize sustainability as part of their branding, while resorts may have larger operational challenges in implementing eco-friendly practices due to scale.

The data presented in **Table 4.3** provides an insightful breakdown of the sizes of accommodations based on the number of rooms they operate. The majority of the respondents manage establishments with **20-49 rooms (56%)**, followed by **50-99 rooms (32%)**. Only a small percentage of businesses operate with **less than 20 rooms (7%)** or **100 or more rooms (6%)**.

Table 4.3: Q3. How many rooms does your establishment have?

Table 4.3: Q3. How many rooms does your establishment have?		
Size of Accommodation	Percentage	Count
Less than 20	7%	5
20 - 49	56%	40
50 - 99	32%	23
100 or more	6%	4
Other	0%	0
Total	100%	72

The size of the accommodation likely influences the feasibility and scale of sustainable practices. Smaller accommodations may have limited resources but greater flexibility, while larger establishments may face higher costs but also have more opportunities to scale sustainable initiatives.

As shown in **Table 4.4**, respondents came from a variety of regions, with **Attica (26%)** and the **Aegean Islands (22%)** being the most represented. Other significant regions included **Crete (18%)**, the **Ionian Islands (8%)**, and **Epirus (7%)**.

Table 4.4: Q4. Which is your region of establishment?

Table 4.4: Q4. Which is your region of establishment?		
Location	Percentage	Count
Attica	26%	19
Aegean, South/North	22%	16
Central Greece	4%	3
Central Macedonia	4%	3
Crete	18%	13
Eastern Macedonia and Thrace	3%	2
Epirus	7%	5
Ionian Islands	8%	6
Peloponnese	4%	3
Thessaly	3%	2
Western Macedonia	0%	0
Western Greece	0%	0
Total	100%	72

This regional distribution is important for understanding how geographical factors such as local regulations, tourist preferences, and environmental conditions affect the adoption of sustainability measures. For example, island-based accommodations might be more focused on resource management due to the limited availability of water and energy resources.

4.2.2 Perceptions of Sustainability

Graphic 4.1 demonstrates that **99%** of respondents consider sustainability a **core value** in their business operations. This near-universal agreement suggests a high level of awareness and commitment to sustainability among SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector.

Chart 4.1: Q5. How important is sustainability to your business operations?

However, the high percentage may also indicate a **social desirability bias**, where businesses feel compelled to present themselves as sustainable even if they face practical challenges in fully integrating these practices into their operations.

Chart 4.2 shows that **67%** of respondents are **extremely well-informed** about sustainability issues, while **25%** are **well-informed**. This high level of awareness suggests that most businesses are not only **aware** of sustainability but also **well-equipped with knowledge**. However, **7%** are only slightly informed, indicating that knowledge gaps still exist. This indicates that while the majority of businesses are aware of sustainability issues, a significant proportion may still lack the deeper knowledge needed to implement more advanced or innovative practices.

Chart 4.2: Q6. How well-informed are you about sustainability issues in the hospitality sector?

4.2.3 Motivations and Values for Adopting Sustainability

The most cited motivation for sustainability investment is **cost savings (40%)**, followed by improving business reputation (**26%**), as shown in **Chart 4.3**. These findings suggest that financial considerations remain the primary driver for sustainability initiatives among SMEs. While **lifestyle choices and personal values** also play a role for **17%** of respondents, **corporate social responsibility** ranks lower, at **13%**.

Chart 4.3: Q7. What motivates you to invest for adopting sustainable practices?

These findings suggest that the financial benefits of sustainability are a key driver, particularly among SMEs where profitability is crucial. However, personal values and reputation also play a significant role, indicating that sustainability is not just seen as an economic imperative but also as a means of building brand value and aligning with personal ethics.

When asked about the values guiding their decisions, (Chart 4.4), **eco-friendly values** (e.g., concern for the environment) were the most frequently cited at **34%** participants, followed by **emotion values** (personal fulfilment) at **32%**. **Humanitarian values** (concern for others' wellbeing) were important to **21%**, while **self-focused values** (improving personal wealth) were cited by **13%** of them.

Chart 4.4: Q8. Which values are important to guide your decisions for sustainable practices?

This reflects a strong alignment with environmental sustainability and personal fulfilment, suggesting that many respondents view sustainability as part of a broader ethical commitment, rather than simply a financial strategy.

4.2.4 Sustainable Strategies and Practices

As seen in Table 4.5, when asked about the implemented measures regarding sustainable strategies and practices, participants answered that the most widely implemented practices are the **reduction of energy consumption (37%)** and the **use of local products (28%)**. This reflects a tendency toward relatively **low-cost, high-impact strategies**, such as energy-saving technologies and local sourcing, which are easy to implement and provide immediate financial benefits.

However, more advanced measures such as **waste management (6%)** and **carbon footprint reduction (2%)** are less widely adopted (Chart 4.5). This suggests that while SMEs are adopting basic sustainability practices, there is room for growth in the implementation of more comprehensive and strategic initiatives, which may require more investment and technical knowledge. The focus on local products also indicates an emphasis on supporting local economies as part of sustainability efforts.

Table 4.5: Q9. What measures have you implemented regarding sustainable strategies?

Table 4.5: Q9. What measures have you implemented regarding sustainable strategies and practices? (Select all that apply)		
Sustainable measures	Percentage	Count
Reduction of energy consumption	37%	68
Reduction of water consumption	8%	14
Waste management	6%	11
Reduction of Carbon footprint	2%	3
Use local products and materials	28%	52
Provision of employment opportunities to locals	14%	26
Offer charity and volunteer participation in local community	1%	2
Implement strategies for equity, diversity and inclusion initiatives	2%	4
No current initiatives	2%	4
Other (please specify)	0%	0
Total	100%	184

Chart 4.5: Q9. What measures have you implemented regarding sustainable strategies?

4.2.5 Barriers to Sustainability

The participants who answered, “No current initiatives!” to the previous question related to the implemented measures regarding sustainable strategies and practices, had the chance to give deeper explanation about the main barriers they encounter. As presented in Table 4.6, high costs of investment are cited as the most significant barrier (50%), followed by uncertainty about return on investment (25%) and insufficient government support (25%).

Table 4.6: Q10. What are the main barriers to implementing sustainable practices?

Table 4.6: Q10. What are the main barriers to implementing sustainable practices in your establishment?		
Please answer ONLY if the previous answer is - No current initiatives! (Select all that apply)		
Type of Barriers	Percentage	Count
Uncertain about the return on investment of implementing sustainable practices	25%	1
High costs of the investments	50%	2
Insufficient government support	25%	1
Lack of knowledge & limited awareness about sustainability actions	0%	0
Other (please specify)	0%	0
Total	100%	4

These findings indicate that while businesses are interested in sustainability, financial concerns are a key barrier for SMEs in adopting sustainability initiatives. The lack of government incentives or support structures exacerbates this problem, limiting the capacity of smaller businesses to make the initial investments required for sustainability.

4.2.6 Impact of Sustainability on Profitability

Table 4.7 shows the results on to what extent have sustainable practices impacted the business's profitability. **94%** of respondents reported a **strongly positive impact** on profitability as a result of their sustainability efforts. This finding is significant, as it demonstrates that businesses perceive economic benefits from adopting sustainable practices, which reinforces the earlier finding that cost savings are a primary motivator.

The **6%** who are **uncertain about the impact** may represent businesses that have recently adopted sustainability measures or have not yet fully quantified the financial benefits.

Table 4.7: Q11. To what extent have sustainable practices impacted your business's profitability

Table 4.7: Q11. To what extent have sustainable practices impacted your business's profitability?		
Profitability Impact	Percentage	Count
Strongly positive impact	94%	68
Strongly negative impact	0%	0
Don't know/Not sure	6%	4
No impact	0%	0
Total	100%	72

4.2.7 Certification and Public Subsidies

As shown in **Chart 4.6**, **68%** of respondents confirmed that they **had received public subsidies** to support the implementation of sustainable strategies. Additionally, **15% had applied for subsidies** awaiting approval, while only **11% had not received any subsidies**. A smaller proportion (**6%**) indicated that they **plan to apply for subsidies** in the future.

Chart 4.6: Q12. Have you received any public subsidies to implement sustainable strategies?

These findings highlight the critical role that public funding plays in facilitating sustainability practices within the hospitality sector. Given that high costs were cited as the primary barrier to sustainability (as discussed in Question 10), public subsidies serve as an essential financial mechanism to alleviate the economic burden on SMEs. The **15%** of businesses that are awaiting approval indicate continued interest in these programs, but also suggest that there may be delays or bottlenecks in the application process that could affect timely implementation.

As shown on **Chart 4.7**, **72%** of respondents had not obtained any form of **Sustainability Certification**. Among those who had, **Green Key** and **Blue Flag** were the most commonly held certifications, both at **7%**, followed by **ISO certifications (4%)** and **Green Tourism (4%)**.

Chart 4.7: Q13. Have you received any of the following Sustainability Certification?

The low level of certification uptake, despite the positive impacts on profitability reported by many businesses (Question 11), suggests several possible reasons. One explanation could be a lack of awareness or understanding about the benefits of certification.

Moreover, the lack of certifications such as **ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) or Climate Neutral** indicates that more advanced or comprehensive certification programs may not be well known or widely pursued among SMEs in Greece.

Regarding the reasons for not obtaining Certification, as shown on **Table 4.8**, the **79%** of respondents cited a **limited understanding of sustainability certifications** as the main reason for not obtaining one. **Practical issues** were mentioned by **15%**, and **6%** reported **challenges with accessing appropriate resources**. Notably, none of the respondents indicated concerns about the **return on investment** or **low market interest**, which shows that perceived value is not the issue, but rather a lack of clarity on the process or benefits of certification.

Table 4.8: Q14. What is the main reason for not obtaining a sustainability certification?

Table 4.8: Q14. What is the main reason for not obtaining a sustainability certification? Please answer ONLY if the previous answer is - No Certification!		
Reasons	Percentage	Count
Limited understanding regarding sustainability certifications	79%	41
Practical issues	15%	8
Market and client interest is low	0%	0
Concerns about return on investment	0%	0
Access to appropriate resources	6%	3
Other (please specify)	0%	0
Total	100%	52

This finding strongly suggests a knowledge gap in the sector. Businesses may recognize the potential market advantages of certification but lack the necessary information or guidance to pursue them. Efforts should be made to raise awareness about the certification process and simplify access to resources that can help businesses become certified.

4.2.8 Future Outlook for Sustainability Investment

Table 4.9 shows that **72%** of respondents are **very likely** to increase their investment in sustainability over the next five years, with another **22%** being **likely**. Only **6%** indicated that they were unlikely to invest further, and none were very unlikely to do so.

Table 4.9: Q15. How likely are you to increase sustainable investment over the next five years?

Table 4.9: Q15. How likely are you to increase sustainable investment over the next five years?		
Future investments	Percentage	Count
Very likely	72%	52
Likely	22%	16
Unlikely	6%	4
Very unlikely	0%	0
Total	100%	72

This overwhelmingly positive outlook suggests a strong commitment to sustainability in the future, which is likely driven by the positive financial impact many businesses have already experienced (as discussed in Question 11). The results also imply that the businesses view sustainability not as a short-term trend, but as a long-term strategic investment that will continue to provide benefits as the market becomes more eco-conscious.

4.3 Discussion and Evaluation

This section presents a critical discussion of the results in relation to the research objectives and questions outlined at the beginning of the study. It aims to evaluate the key findings presented in the previous section and analyse their implications for the Greek hospitality sector’s sustainability practices, with reference to existing literature and theoretical frameworks.

4.3.1 Summary of Key Findings

The study sought to explore the **motivations, values, and practices** influencing the adoption of sustainability initiatives in SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector.

The findings provided insights into the operational characteristics, sustainability initiatives, and the challenges faced by these businesses. The key findings can be summarized as follows:

1. The majority of respondents manage medium-sized accommodations with 20-49 rooms (56%), and most have been operating for 5-10 years (40%) (Table 4.3 and Table 4.1).
2. Sustainability is considered a core value for almost all respondents (99%) (Chart 4.1), and most businesses are well-informed about sustainability issues (92%) (Chart 4.2).
3. The primary motivation for adopting sustainability is cost savings (40%), followed by improving business reputation (26%) (Chart 4.3).
4. The eco-friendly values (e.g., concern for the environment) were the most frequently cited at 34% and emotion values (personal fulfillment) was referred at 32% of the responses (Chart 4.4).
5. The most commonly implemented practices are energy reduction (37%) and the use of local products (28%), with more advanced strategies, such as waste management and carbon footprint reduction, being less common (Table 4.5 & Chart 4.5).
6. The key barriers to sustainability adoption are high costs (50%) and uncertainty about return on investment (25%) (Table 4.6).
7. Most businesses report that sustainability has had a strongly positive impact on their profitability (94%) (Table 4.9).
8. The majority of respondents (68%) confirmed that they had received public subsidies to support the implementation of sustainable strategies (Chart 4.5).
9. The 72% of respondents have not obtained any form of Sustainability Certification, citing a lack of understanding as the main reason (79%) (Table 4.7). Among those who had, Green Key and Blue Flag were the most commonly held certifications, both at 7%, followed by ISO certifications (4%) and Green Tourism (4%) (Chart 4.7).
10. The reasons for not obtaining Certification, for the 79% of participants, was the limited understanding of sustainability certifications (Table 4.8).
11. 72% of respondents are very likely to increase their investment in sustainability over the next five years (Table 4.9).

4.3.2 Addressing the Research Objectives

Research Objective 1: To Explore the Motivations and Values for Sustainability Adoption in the Greek Hospitality Sector

The findings clearly demonstrate that cost savings (40%) are the primary motivation for Greek hospitality businesses to adopt sustainability practices. This aligns with economic theories of business behavior, particularly for SMEs, where cost minimization is a major driver for decision-making. As illustrated in (Chart 4.3), businesses are primarily driven by financial benefits, with secondary motivations linked to improving business reputation (26%).

However, the fact that personal values and lifestyle choices also play a significant role for 17% of respondents suggests that sustainability is not solely an economic decision but is also influenced by ethical considerations. This finding supports the work of Font et al. (2016), who highlighted that sustainability adoption in SMEs is often linked to the personal beliefs of the owner or manager, particularly in sectors like hospitality, where service quality and brand identity are intertwined with corporate values.

Research Objective 2: To Examine the Sustainability Practices Adopted by Greek SMEs in the Hospitality Sector

The findings suggest that most businesses have implemented basic sustainability practices such as energy reduction (37%) and the use of local products (28%) (Table 4.5). These practices are relatively low-cost and offer immediate benefits in terms of operational efficiency. However, more advanced practices, such as waste management (6%) and carbon footprint reduction (2%), are less frequently adopted.

This indicates that while there is widespread commitment to sustainability as a concept, the depth of implementation remains limited, particularly with regard to environmental impact reduction. These findings are consistent with previous research by Kornilaki and Font (2019), who found that SMEs in the hospitality sector often focus on incremental changes that align with existing business models rather than adopting transformational sustainability initiatives.

Research Objective 3: To Identify the Barriers to Sustainability Adoption in Greek Hospitality SMEs

The most significant barriers identified were high costs (50%) and uncertainty about return on investment (25%) (Table 4.6). These findings are in line with the literature, which frequently cites financial constraints as a key obstacle for SMEs when adopting sustainability practices. The high initial costs of investments in energy efficiency or renewable technologies, for instance, are often prohibitive for smaller businesses that operate on tight margins.

Interestingly, despite the positive impact on profitability reported by 94% of respondents (Table 4.7), there remains a perceived risk associated with sustainability investment. This indicates a possible disconnect between perception and reality, where businesses are aware of the potential long-term benefits but are hesitant to commit due to short-term financial pressures or lack of support. These findings highlight the need for greater institutional support and financial incentives to encourage broader adoption.

4.3.3 Discussion on Survey Findings and Existing Research

The results of this study align with several key themes from existing literature but also extend our understanding in certain areas, particularly regarding the motivations, values, barriers, and practical adoption of sustainability measures.

The finding that cost savings (40%) are the primary motivation for sustainability adoption (Chart 4.3) is consistent with previous research. Studies have repeatedly shown that SMEs are often driven by economic factors when adopting sustainability practices, particularly in resource-constrained sectors like hospitality. Revell, Stokes, and Chen (2010) found that small businesses

primarily engage in environmental practices when there is a clear economic benefit, such as reducing energy costs or increasing operational efficiency.

In the Greek hospitality sector, cost savings are a key driver of sustainability adoption, particularly for SMEs. However, this financial motivation is intertwined with other regional and cultural factors. In regions with stringent environmental regulations, such as parts of Italy and Spain, compliance costs also incentivize sustainable practices (Kornilaki and Font, 2019). Comparatively, Greece, like other Mediterranean countries, faces similar environmental challenges (e.g., resource scarcity), but cultural pride in local traditions, like sourcing local products, plays a role in sustainability efforts. While Greece focuses on cost-effective, incremental sustainability changes, other nations, such as Spain, have adopted more extensive eco-certifications.

Similarly, Kornilaki and Font (2019) reported that economic incentives, including cost savings and increased competitiveness, were the main drivers for SMEs in the tourism industry to implement sustainability strategies. The fact that improving business reputation was the second most cited motivation (26%) aligns with the growing body of literature that emphasizes consumer demand for sustainable practices. According to Font, Garay, and Jones (2016), businesses in the tourism sector are increasingly aware that sustainability enhances their brand image and differentiates them from competitors, making it a valuable marketing tool.

However, the 17% of businesses motivated by personal values and lifestyle choices highlights the role of ethical motivations in sustainability adoption. This supports Stern et al. (1999) value-belief-norm theory, which posits that personal values and moral responsibility can drive pro-environmental behaviors, even when financial incentives are secondary. This suggests that, for a subset of SMEs, sustainability is linked not only to profitability but also to corporate identity and the personal ethics of the owner or manager.

The finding that high costs of investment (50%) and uncertainty about return on investment (25%) are the primary barriers to adopting sustainability (Table 4.6) mirrors results from numerous studies on SMEs and sustainability. For example, Brammer, Hojmoser, and Marchant (2012) found that many SMEs hesitate to adopt sustainability measures because of cost concerns, particularly the initial capital investment required for technologies like renewable energy or water-saving infrastructure.

This is further supported by Revell and Blackburn (2007), who highlighted that while many SMEs recognize the importance of sustainability, the financial constraints and perceived risks often prevent them from implementing more environmental strategies. Moreover, the uncertainty about return on investment aligns with Jenkins (2009), who found that SMEs are often unwilling to commit to long-term sustainability projects due to the difficulty of quantifying potential benefits in the short term.

Despite these barriers, the overwhelmingly positive impact of sustainability on profitability (94%, Table 4.7) challenges the perception of high costs as a deterrent. Studies such as Epstein and Buhovac (2014) have shown that while the initial costs of sustainability investments can be significant, the long-term financial gains through energy savings, customer loyalty, and reduced regulatory risks often outweigh these initial expenditures. This suggests that businesses need

more information on the long-term financial benefits of sustainability, which could help alleviate concerns about upfront costs and uncertain returns.

One of the more striking findings is the low rate of sustainability certification (72% of businesses have not obtained any form of certification, Chart 4.7), with the primary reason being a limited understanding of the process (79%, Table 4.8). This supports research by Tilley (1999), which found that many SMEs, especially in sectors like hospitality, lack the knowledge and resources to pursue certification. This lack of understanding can be attributed to the complexity and cost of certification processes, which are often seen as bureaucratic and time-consuming for small businesses with limited staffing and financial capacity.

Font and Harris (2004) similarly argued that while sustainability certifications like ISO 14001 or Green Key provide clear environmental benefits and can enhance a company's reputation, the administrative burden and lack of immediate market demand discourage many SMEs from pursuing certification. This highlights a key area where policy interventions and educational programs could help bridge the knowledge gap and provide businesses with clearer guidance on how certifications can enhance both their operational efficiency and market competitiveness.

This finding aligns with the broader trend in hospitality, as highlighted by Gössling et al. (2011), who emphasized that tourism businesses are increasingly viewing sustainability as a long-term investment rather than a cost. Similarly, Sheldon and Park (2011) found that sustainability is no longer viewed as an optional extra but as a core component of business strategy, particularly in competitive tourism markets where consumer expectations for eco-friendly practices are rising.

However, as Font and McCabe (2017) caution, the success of sustainability initiatives often depends on the availability of institutional support and regulatory frameworks that incentivise long-term investment. In this regard, the role of public subsidies (68% of businesses had received subsidies, Chart 4.6), will be crucial in helping SMEs overcome the initial financial hurdles and sustain their commitment to environmental practices.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The research aimed to explore the motivations, values, practices, and barriers influencing the adoption of sustainability initiatives among SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector. The study highlights that sustainability is widely regarded as a core value by the majority of respondents (99%), but the depth of sustainability adoption remains limited to basic practices such as energy conservation and local sourcing. The primary driver of sustainability adoption was cost savings (40%), while high costs and uncertainty about return on investment were identified as the most significant barriers.

Furthermore, while sustainability was recognised as a long-term strategic priority by most businesses, the study revealed a significant lack of certification (72%) and a knowledge gap regarding the benefits and processes of sustainability certifications. This reflects the need for better educational support and financial incentives to encourage broader and deeper sustainability adoption across the sector.

5.2 Limitations of the Project

Although this study provided valuable insights, several limitations should be acknowledged:

- ❖ The sample size of 72 respondents limits the generalisability of the findings. Although the survey covered a diverse range of businesses, including boutique hotels, guesthouses, and resorts, it focused exclusively on SMEs in the Greek hospitality sector. Future studies could expand the scope to include larger businesses or other sectors of the tourism industry, such as restaurants or transport providers.
- ❖ The research employed a quantitative approach using structured surveys. While this allowed for clear identification of patterns and relationships, it did not capture the qualitative nuances of how individual businesses approach sustainability. Incorporating qualitative methods, such as interviews, could provide deeper insights into personal motivations and strategic decision-making processes.
- ❖ The reliance on self-reported data introduces potential biases. Respondents may have over-reported their commitment to sustainability, either due to social desirability bias or because they want to align their responses with perceived expectations. Future research could include direct observations or third-party assessments of sustainability practices.
- ❖ While the study covered businesses from different regions of Greece, it did not deeply explore how regional regulations, cultural factors, or tourism dynamics may influence sustainability practices. This may have led to an underappreciation of regional variations in sustainability adoption.

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the research findings, the following recommendations are proposed to address the barriers and enhance sustainability practices in the Greek hospitality sector (**Figure 5**):

Figure 5: Recommendations for sustainable strategies in the Greek hospitality sector

Source: Own designing

1. Establishment of **targeted financial incentives for SMEs**, including subsidies, tax credits, and low-interest loans specifically for green technology investments such as renewable energy systems, waste reduction technologies, and water-saving innovations.

The primary barrier to sustainability identified in the research was the high cost of investments (50%) (Table 4.6), which is consistent with findings from Revell and Blackburn (2007), who also found that SMEs face significant financial constraints when implementing sustainability practices. Financial incentives tailored to the needs of SMEs can alleviate upfront costs and could be supported by funding programs which provide financial and technical support to small businesses to comply with environmental regulations and adopt sustainable practices (Stokes et al., 2007).

Government policy plays a crucial role in helping businesses overcome financial challenges related to sustainability. Specific policy reforms could include offering tax incentives or low-interest loans for companies investing in renewable energy or waste management systems. Greece could adopt successful initiatives from countries like Spain, which has implemented an "Energy Efficiency Fund" providing grants to SMEs for eco-friendly upgrades, (European Commission, 2020) or Italy's "Eco-Bonus" scheme (European Investment Bank, 2020), offering tax deductions for sustainability projects. Tailoring similar policies to Greece's tourism sector would encourage broader adoption of sustainability practices, making it financially viable for SMEs.

The recommendation to develop targeted financial support is entrepreneurial because it encourages public-private partnerships where government subsidies work hand-in-hand with business innovation.

2. Implementation of **region-specific training programs** that offer education on sustainability certifications and their benefits. These programs should include workshops, online courses, and consulting services to help SMEs understand the process of obtaining certifications like ISO 14001, Green Key, and Blue Flag.

The low uptake of certifications (72% of businesses not certified, Chart 4.7) is largely due to a lack of understanding about the process and benefits of certification (79% of respondents, Table 4.8). Previous studies, such as Font and Harris (2004), have found that many SMEs perceive certifications as costly, bureaucratic, and time-consuming, with unclear immediate benefits. By increasing access to education and training, businesses can better understand the long-term advantages of certification, including enhanced marketability, regulatory compliance, and customer trust.

This recommendation is entrepreneurial because it focuses on creating a sustainability ecosystem within the Greek hospitality sector, empowering SMEs with the knowledge and tools to succeed in the global green tourism market.

3. Creation of **regional sustainability networks** or **clusters** of SMEs that can collaborate on shared sustainability goals, including resource sharing, joint investments in sustainable infrastructure, and knowledge exchange on best practices.

One of the challenges faced by SMEs is the isolated nature of their efforts, which limits their ability to access the necessary resources or technology to implement sustainability on a large scale. Research by Kelliher and Reindl (2009) supports the idea that SMEs benefit from networking and collaborative initiatives, particularly when it comes to sharing expertise, costs, and innovative solutions for sustainability.

The entrepreneurial nature of this recommendation lies in the creation of regional sustainability hubs, which encourage co-investment in green technologies, reducing the financial burden on individual businesses.

4. Development of a **digital platform** tailored to SMEs in the hospitality sector, offering resources such as self-assessment tools, sustainability guides, and access to green technology providers. The platform could also serve as a marketplace for sustainability certifications, enabling businesses to compare certification options and track their progress toward achieving green standards.

According to Tilley (1999), SMEs often lack the internal expertise to navigate complex environmental regulations and certification processes, making it difficult for them to adopt best practices. A digital platform could bridge this gap by providing customised resources that are specifically designed for SMEs in the hospitality sector.

This recommendation is highly innovative, leveraging digital technology to provide a one-stop solution for SMEs. The platform could include features such as sustainability scorecards, allowing businesses to self-assess their environmental impact, and virtual consultations with sustainability experts.

5. Establishment of **Public-Private Partnerships** (PPPs) aimed at creating sustainable tourism zones where businesses, local governments, and sustainability organizations collaborate on green infrastructure projects.

According to Brammer, Hojmosse, and Marchant (2012), PPPs provide a way to leverage public sector investment in infrastructure while encouraging private sector innovation. By working together, governments can provide the initial funding for large-scale sustainability projects, while private businesses benefit from lower operating costs and improved sustainability outcomes.

One effective way for companies in the Greek hospitality sector to overcome financial barriers is by forming strategic partnerships. SMEs can collaborate through regional sustainability networks, where resources are pooled, and collective investments in green technologies, such as solar energy systems or water conservation measures can reduce costs for individual businesses. These networks may also facilitate knowledge sharing, allowing smaller firms to learn best practices from peers who have successfully implemented sustainable strategies. Public-private partnerships (PPPs) present another opportunity, where the government and private sector co-invest in sustainability projects, thereby lowering the upfront costs for businesses. For instance, municipalities could partner with hotels to fund and maintain shared waste management systems or renewable energy projects, which would benefit both the businesses and the local community.

This recommendation represents an entrepreneurial approach to sustainability by fostering cooperation between the public and private sectors to achieve common goals. The creation of sustainable tourism zones would help SMEs access shared resources, which would be too costly for individual businesses to establish independently.

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7 APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Questionnaire

Welcome Message

This survey is part of Panagiota Akgoli's MBA thesis at the University of Northampton, Faculty of Business and Law. Your input is invaluable to the success of this research.

The questionnaire consists of only 15 multiple-choice questions and should take no more than 2 - 3 minutes to complete.

Please note that all responses are anonymous, and your data will be handled in full compliance with GDPR regulations. Your privacy is of utmost importance, and the information you provide will be used solely for the purposes of this academic research.

Thank you for your time and contribution!

Consent Confirmation

Before we proceed, please confirm the following:

- I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw at any time without penalty.
- I understand that my responses are anonymous and will be treated in compliance with GDPR regulations.
- I consent to the use of my responses for academic research purposes.

Section 1: Profile of Participants

1. What type of accommodation do you own/manage?

- Hotel
- Boutique Hotel
- Guesthouse
- Resort
- Other

2. How many rooms does your establishment have?

- Less than 20
- 20-49
- 50-99
- 100 or more

3. How long has your establishment been in operation?

- Being established
- Less than 5 years
- 5-10 years
- More than 10 years

4. Which is your region of establishment?

- Attica
- Aegean, South/North
- Eastern Macedonia and Thrace

- Epirus
- Crete
- Central Macedonia
- Central Greece
- Ionian Islands
- Peloponnese
- Thessaly
- Western Macedonia
- Western Greece

Section 2: Perceptions of Sustainability

5. How important is sustainability to your business operations?

- Sustainability is a core value in all our operations
- Not important at all

6. How well-informed are you about sustainability issues in the hospitality sector?

- Extremely well informed
- Well informed
- Slightly informed
- Not informed at all

Section 3: Motivations and Values for Sustainability

7. What motivates you to invest for adopting sustainable practices? (Select all that apply)

- Cost savings
- Improve my business's reputation
- Lifestyle choices and personal values
- Corporate social responsibility
- No reason for investing in sustainability
- Other (please specify)

8. Which of the following values you consider important in guiding your decisions regarding sustainable practices? (Select all that apply)

- Emotion values (e.g., personal fulfilment)
- Self-focused values (e.g., improving personal wealth)
- Humanitarian values (e.g., concern for others' wellbeing)
- Eco-friendly values (e.g., concern for the environment)
- Other (please specify)

Section 5: Sustainable Strategies and Practices

9. What measures have you implemented or plan to implement regarding sustainable strategies and practices? (Select all that apply)

- Reduction of energy consumption
- Reduction of water consumption
- Waste management
- Reduction of Carbon footprint
- Use local products and materials
- Provision of employment opportunities to locals
- Offer charity and volunteer participation in local community

- Implement strategies for equity, diversity and inclusion initiatives
- No current initiatives
- Other (please specify)

**10. What are the main barriers to implementing sustainable practices in your establishment?
(Select all that apply)**

Please answer ONLY if the previous answer is - No current initiatives!

- Uncertain about the return on investment of implementing sustainable practices
- High costs of the investments
- Lack of knowledge & limited awareness about sustainability actions
- Insufficient government support
- Other (please specify)

Section 6: Impact of Sustainability on Profitability

11. To what extent have sustainable practices impacted your business's profitability?

- Strongly positive impact
- Strongly negative impact
- No impact

Section 7: Certification and Public Subsidies

**12. Have you received any public subsidies to implement sustainable strategies and practices?
(Select all that apply)**

- Yes
- Have currently applied
- No
- Plan to apply in the future

13. Have you received any sustainability certification?

- Green Key
- ISO 14001, ISO21204, ISO 22000
- Travelife Certified
- Blue Flag
- ESG or GRI Certification
- Climate Neutral
- Green Destinations
- Green Tourism
- No Certification
- Other (please specify)

14. What is the main reason for not obtaining a sustainability certification?

Please answer ONLY if the previous answer is - No Certification!

- Limited understanding regarding sustainability certifications
- Practical issues
- Market and client interest is low
- Concerns about return on investment
- Access to appropriate resources

- Other (please specify)

Section 8: Future Outlook for Sustainability Investment

15. How likely are you to proceed or increase your investment in sustainable practices over the next five years?

- Very unlikely
- Unlikely
- Likely
- Very likely

Success Message

Thank You for Completing the Survey!

Your responses have been successfully recorded.

I greatly appreciate your time and effort in contributing to my MBA thesis research at the University of Northampton, Faculty of Business and Law.

Your participation is invaluable to the success of this study.

Thank you once again for your support!